

Redefining Port Call Processes: The Role of Automation and Emerging Technologies

Dr Anastasia Roukouni¹, Giannis Kanellopoulos¹, Konstantinos Louzis², Alexandros Koimtzoglou², Dr Nikolaos P. Ventikos² and Dr Angelos Amditis¹

1. I-SENSE Group/Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Athens, Greece
2. Laboratory for Maritime Transport, School of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering, NTUA, Athens, Greece

Corresponding author: anastasia.roukouni@iccs.gr

Abstract: *The present paper explores the automation of vessel port call processes as a critical advancement in maritime logistics, within the framework of the EU-funded AutoMoTIF project. It presents a comprehensive simulation-based use case that incorporates autonomous tugboats and Automated Mooring Systems (AMS) to enhance the berthing and unberthing of freight vessels. Key technologies, operational frameworks, and coordination protocols are analyzed, while a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) evaluation framework is proposed to assess the operational, safety, environmental, economic, and societal impacts of automation. Moreover, the research introduces an Open Reference Architecture for Digital Twins (DTs), offering a modular and interoperable design tailored to smart port operations. This work contributes to the broader digital transformation of maritime logistics, promoting efficiency, resilience, and sustainability within multimodal supply chains.*

Keywords: *Maritime automation, port call optimization, Digital Twins (DT), Physical Internet (PI), autonomous tugboats, hyperconnected freight transport, smart logistics*

Physical Internet (PI) Roadmap Fitness: PI Networks, System of Logistics Networks

Targeted Delivery Mode-s: Paper, In-Person presentation

1 Introduction

Automation has brought drastic changes in many different disciplines during the last decades, with freight transportation being one of them. While this evolution has opened new prospects, a number of new challenges (De Alvis and Nam, 2024) and uncertainties (Dekhne et al., 2019) associated with it made their appearance as well. Advanced technologies have been adapted across all stages of the supply chain to address the growing demand for faster and more efficient product delivery (Yang et al., 2021). As a key component of the freight industry, maritime transport is also undergoing significant transformations, driven by the increasing use of technological innovations and digitalization introduced to enhance safety, efficiency and sustainability (Andrei and Scarlat, 2024).

The paper is part of the on-going research conducted in the context of the EU-funded AutoMoTIF project. In this project, different use cases are employed to extract relevant user needs and understand technological gaps which lead to the development of technical specifications, different scenarios and concepts of operations, capturing different parts of the freight transport and logistics chain. One of these use cases focuses on investigating the potential advantages of utilizing automation across all phases of the port call process. The

overarching objective is to identify the basic requirements for a seamless automated port call process - this initially includes the vessel's arrival at the port, entailing the initial announcement, allocation of berth windows as well as the tugboats assignment, and continues with the vessel's manoeuvring and docking processes, both performed by the assigned tugboats. This is followed by the stevedoring operations that secure the vessel on the quay to initiate the cargo loading and unloading processes.

The relevance of this research to the Physical Internet (PI) concept lies in its alignment with the PI's vision of hyperconnected, interoperable logistics networks (Montreuil, 2011). (REF) By introducing automation and standardized digital systems into the port call process, this study supports the seamless integration of maritime operations into larger, intermodal logistics ecosystems. Moreover, the AutoMoTIF open architecture framework proposed for Digital Twins promotes modularity and data transparency—key principles of the Physical Internet—which can ultimately enable real-time coordination between sea, rail, and land-based logistics, reducing fragmentation and maximizing resource efficiency

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Initially, a state-of-the-art analysis of automated vessel calls is presented, followed by the description of the automated call process as approached by the use case of AutoMoTIF. After that, the key performance indicators that will be used to evaluate the results of the use case are outlined. Finally, the adaptation of the proposed a new AutoMoTIF open reference architecture framework to the specific use case is discussed and some general conclusions are drawn.

2 State-of-the-art analysis of automated vessel calls

The automation of vessel port call processes is a critical part of automating freight transport in general, as they can be found in the intersection of maritime vessels with land-based logistics networks. The calls comprise well-coordinated procedures that facilitate the seamless movement of goods across borders and supply chains. Port call optimization needs to be integrated with inbound and outbound logistics. Port operations are complex as they are intended to serve sea and land transport simultaneously and consist of multiple actors who must act cooperatively for the port to be an effective hub. The actors and systems involved in the automated port call process concept are the following: Berth Allocation System (BAS), tugboat personnel, autonomous tugboats, vessel, Automated Mooring System (AMS), Shore Control Centre (SCC) operator, Vessel Traffic System (VTS) operator.

Current research on vessel automation is primarily focused on enhancing vessel autonomy through the development of sophisticated navigation and control systems, addressing communication and connectivity challenges, improving situational awareness for collision avoidance and safety, and exploring commercial viability and necessary regulatory frameworks. However, there are significant gaps related to the automated operation of vessels when calling ports. Research that investigates parts of this process has been conducted in the context of EC-funded projects such as MOSES, AEGIS, AUTOSHIP and SEAMLESS focusing mainly on autonomous ship navigation, automated loading and unloading, automated manoeuvring and docking and shore control stations that deal with the exchange of data required for the technical integration rather than the business one (Segura et al., 2025).

The exchange of crucial information such as stowage plans, loading/discharging plans, berthing place, etc. are often ignored thus making the adoption of automated vessel operations for commercial exploitation practically impossible. The vessel calls phases involve a complex interplay of activities implemented by different technologies, as presented in the following

diagram (Figure 1). The differentiation in colour demonstrates that cargo operations (in orange) is a phase that is out of scope of the use case discussed herein.

Figure 1: The different stages of a port call process

Planning for arrival: The logistical planning for a port operation typically encompasses the scheduling of berths and quay cranes, the planning of vessel routes, and the accurate prediction of vessel arrival times. However, a significant challenge arises from the frequent deviations of ships from their anticipated arrival times, which can lead to disruptions in the plan. The technologies involved in the planning for arrival stage are described in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1: Planning for arrival technologies

Planning for arrival	
Port Management System (PMS) / Terminal Operating Systems (TOS)	Description: Integrated software solutions are developed to manage internal port operations efficiently. Port authorities and terminal operators have the responsibility for managing port facilities and operations. Over recent decades, these systems have undergone significant advancements, integrating cutting-edge technologies to enhance their functionality and effectiveness (Hernandez et al., 2024).
	Current Applications: PMS/TOS is currently integrated in large ports, which have a high volume of traffic and arrival.
Port Collaborative Decision Making (PortCDM)	Description: PortCDM facilitates the exchange of operational information among key stakeholders involved in port call processes. By centralizing all port call-related events in a single platform, the system provides a unified view of operations, enabling better coordination and optimized planning for all parties. (Lind et al., 2019).
	Current Applications: PortCDM meets the demands from shipping companies to adjust just-in-time arrivals and departures.
Port Community Systems (PCS)	Description: PCS are digital collaborative platforms that enable seamless exchange of information among a port's many stakeholders. By integrating the various systems, the PCS reduces duplication of effort, saves time, and improves communication among all stakeholders. (Prasad et al., 2023).
	Current Applications: fourth wave of PCS, since 2018. PCS are based on multimodal service offerings, offered on the cloud and linked to other external digital logistics platforms, adopting Industry 4.0 technologies.
Vessel Traffic System (VTS)	Description: VTS is a maritime traffic monitoring system operated by port authorities to ensure safe and efficient vessel movements in the port area. The system uses radars, Automatic Identification System (AIS), and CCTV to track vessels in real time (Vessel Traffic Services, n.d.).
	Current Applications: Operators provide real-time guidance and instructions to the vessel, coordinating traffic and preventing collisions with other ships.
Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)	Description: RFID is a technology that uses radio waves to identify and track container movements within the port, from arrival to loading/unloading. They consist of RFID tags (small electronic devices) and RFID readers that transmit and receive radio signals (Shi, et al., 2011). They are also used in Automated Gate Operations, allowing the entry and exit of trucks and containers, and for automated data collection and paperless transactions.

	<u>Current Applications:</u> largely implemented in operational procedures in port-based container logistics. (Shi et al., 2011)
Satellite communication systems	<u>Description:</u> Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) Satellite Connectivity, MEO Satellite (GNSS) and GEO Satellites (SATCOM) provides reliable and high-speed internet access to ships operating, telecommunications, broadcasting and weather forecasting (IEC Telecom, 2023).
	<u>Current Applications:</u> While MEO and GEO are mature technologies, LEO satellites are considered relatively mature.

Berthing and unberthing: Proper berthing is crucial for ensuring safety, efficiency, and the smooth operation of maritime activities. It requires coordination between the vessel's crew and port authorities, as well as consideration of factors such as tide, weather, and vessel size. By incorporating the technologies presented in Table 2, ports can improve the efficiency and safety of berthing operations, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of maritime transport. Unberthing and departure are the concluding phases of a vessel's stay in port, marking the beginning of its voyage. These processes require careful coordination, precision, and adherence to safety protocols.

Table 2: Berthing/Unberthing technologies

Berthing / Unberthing	
Berth Allocation System (BAS)	<u>Description:</u> The Berth Allocation Systems optimizes the allocation of berths to vessels, providing a solution to the Berth Allocation Problem (BAP), a logistical challenge that arises in ports when determining how to optimally allocate available berths to incoming vessels to minimize waiting times. Existing different categories of BAP: discrete (for berthing and unberthing), continuous, and hybrid. Many studies have focused on single quay, and few for the Multi-Quay BAP (Aslam et al. 2023)
	<u>Current Applications:</u> The single quay is the most used (Port of Limassol in Cyprus, has seven continuous berthing quays) while the implementation of the multiple quays is currently underway.
Dynamic Positioning Systems (DPS)	<u>Description:</u> DPS is an advanced technology used to maintain a vessel's position and heading without the use of anchors making it easier to control their movements during berthing and unberthing operations. The implementation of DPS requires the vessel to be equipped with azimuth type propulsion, instead of the conventional rudder-propeller arrangement.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> DPS is currently used in special purpose vessels, such as Offshore Support Vessels, tugboats, small cargo ships.
Automated Berthing System (ABS)	<u>Description:</u> ABS focuses on the physical process of docking a ship by using advanced algorithms and sensors (e.g. LIDAR) onboard to help ships dock safely and efficiently using their own propulsion means.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> ABS is currently in the research and development phase with some successful pilot demonstrations of vessels berthing automatically in Europe and Japan ^{1,2} .
Terminal Logic Control Interface (TLC)	<u>Description:</u> Refers to a system or interface used to manage and control terminal activities effectively. TLC can automate several processes, such as gate operations, cargo tracking, and billing, reducing manual intervention and increasing accuracy.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> currently used in automatic stacking and automated cranes and vehicles, integrated with TOS and PCS for better coordination with stakeholders.
Terrestrial digital communications	<u>Description:</u> Terrestrial digital communications enable connectivity and real-time data exchange for IoT devices, machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, and user group alerting services.

¹ <https://www.nippon.com/en/japan-topics/g02047/>

² <https://maritime-executive.com/article/european-space-agency-sponsors-grimaldi-project-for-automated-berthing>

	<p>Low-Power Wide-Area Network: -LoRaWAN and 0G Network technology: Used to connect low-power sensors over long distances using low energy. It enables low-bandwidth, low-power communication. Ideal for IoT sensor communication that does not require high data rates, such as container location and environmental condition monitoring. -Cellular networks: 4G LTE and 5G connects mobile devices and sensors in real-time providing low latency and higher data speeds, ideal for more complex applications. In ports, they give access to remote control of cranes, autonomous vehicles, and real-time logistics management in the port.</p> <p><u>Current applications:</u> Terrestrial digital communication technologies are increasingly essential in the context of ships equipped with intelligent technologies.</p>
<p>Automated Mooring Systems (AMS)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> AMS are advanced technologies used in ports to securely and efficiently moor vessels. They are essentially robotic systems that can automatically handle the process of attaching and detaching mooring lines to a vessel, or that eliminate the need for using mooring lines completely by using vacuum-based attachment methods. These systems reduce the need for manual labour and minimize the risks associated with handling mooring lines both onboard the vessel by the Deck team and onshore and by the port stevedores.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Examples of existing AMS include Trelleborg's³ AutoMoor™ and Cavotec's⁴ Moormaster™ vacuum-based systems, Mampaey's Intelligent Dock Locking System⁵ magnetic mooring system, and MacGregor's⁶ robotic system for handling mooring lines.</p>
<p>Information Systems</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Ports are increasingly implementing systems that exploit real-time information from sensors (e.g. weather, air quality etc.) in order to facilitate decision-making in port operations.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> An example application is the Port of Rotterdam that has implemented a smart mooring solution as part of their digitalisation strategy to predict the impact that storms and adverse weather will have on moored vessels, providing users in the port with the much-needed time to prepare and avoid incidents in the port. (Port Technology International, 2021).</p>
<p>Autonomous Tugboats</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Autonomous tugboats are highly automated vessels equipped with advanced technology, incl. sensors, computers, and propulsion systems that enable them to navigate and manoeuvre with minimal or no human intervention.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Automated tugboats are not a fully mature technology, and they are not widely implemented, although significant advancements are being made. Several industry-led projects have explored the capabilities of autonomous tugboats, including the following (Hensen, 2021): 2017: remote control demonstration of the Svitzer Hermod in the port of Copenhagen (Rolls-Royce and Svitzer). 2018: remote control demonstration of the Kotug RT Bocum in the port of Rotterdam from a control station in Marseille. 2020: Intellitug project that aims to retrofit a harbour tug for enabling autonomous navigation (Wärtsilä, PSA Marine, Lloyd's Register, the Technology Centre for Offshore and Marine Singapore (TCOMS), and co-funded by Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore's Maritime Innovation and Technology Fund). 2021: RECOTUG project aimed at developing a remotely controlled tugboat capable of conducting a full towage operation (Svitzer A/S, Kongsberg Maritime and ABS). 2021: Damen designed and built tugboat Nellie Bly, outfitted with the Sea Machines Robotics autonomy system SM300, which conducted 342 collision avoidance manoeuvres during a 1000 nm voyage around Denmark while being remotely controlled from the US⁷.</p>

³ <https://www.trelleborg.com/en/marine-and-infrastructure/products-solutions-and-services/marine/docking-and-mooring/automated-mooring-systems/automoor>

⁴ <https://www.cavotec.com/en/your-applications/ports-maritime/automated-mooring>

⁵ <https://twd.nl/projects/structural-design-for-mampaey-intelligent-docklocking-system/>

⁶ <https://www.macgregor.com/intelligent-solutions/automated-mooring-system/>

⁷ <https://www.rivieramm.com/news-content-hub/news-content-hub/halfway-mark-reached-for-the-autonomous-machine-odyssey-67916>

<p>Furthermore, the EU-funded research project MOSES developed a concept for an autonomous tugboat swarm that is monitored through a remote-control station. The project developed a machine-learning based algorithm for controlling the swarm and demonstrated the concept in a Pilot demonstration in Denmark.</p>

The automation of the port call process relates to the governance, operational, and digital dimensions of the Physical Internet, which have been identified by Fahim et al. (2021a) with respect to port development. In terms of governance, rules and protocols will need to be developed to facilitate interconnectivity between the different actors and autonomous systems involved in the process. In the operational dimension, automation will change how the manoeuvring and mooring operations are conducted by integrating the tugboats and mooring systems as autonomous agents. In the digital dimension, the various information systems that need to be integrated will facilitate information flow through the different parts of the transport network and support decision-making.

Specifically, the automated port call process will contribute to the following port performance criteria, which have been identified by Fahim et al. (2021b) and are expected to play a role in port selection in the Physical Internet paradigm. The quality of the port's Level of Service (LoS) will be increased by minimizing the time to berth to which an increase in availability of port tugboat services will also contribute. Automating tugboat and mooring services are expected to improve safety as less humans will be involved in hazardous tasks, as well as improving the level of the port's automation. Furthermore, the automation and the level of network interconnectivity, which will be required to acquire the necessary information from the supply chain (i.e. calling vessel characteristics, type of cargo) and the port (i.e. berth availability), will increase the port's "smartness" with respect to optimizing the manoeuvring and the berth allocation processes.

3 The automated port call process in AutoMoTIF

In AutoMoTIF, the entire process of berthing and unberthing will be simulated at a generic port (i.e. container terminal), to replicate the complex interactions among the process key players under the assumption that the operation will be performed by fully autonomous tugboats (i.e., without a master onboard) and that an Automated Mooring System (AMS) is installed at the quay. The simulation will incorporate various key parameters for the process, such as weather conditions, size of the vessel, number of tugboats, significant wave etc. The outcome of the simulation, together with the results of the rest of AutoMoTIF use cases that will simulate automated port operations, automated shunting as a service-oriented platform and automated multimodal terminal operations, will then be used to validate a new proposed open reference architecture framework for Digital Twins (DT), one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field.

During the planning of arrival phase, the vessel provides the port the ship-specific data as required by the Maritime Single Window (e.g. length, draught, type of cargo, Estimated Time of Arrival, EDI files, etc). Using this information combined with the maritime traffic at the port,

Figure 2: Diagram of interactions between components in the automation framework

the BAS assigns the vessel to a berth. When the vessel reaches the anchorage, the autonomous tugboats receive a mission profile from the BAS, which includes the vessel characteristics, the location where they will meet the vessel, and the location of the allocated berth (Figure 2). The mission profile is also sent to the AMS that is positioned at the allocated berth. The autonomous tugboats

navigate towards the designated meeting point and the tow lines are secured by the onboard personnel.

During the autonomous manoeuvring process, the autonomous tugboats receive information from external information systems, such as the VTS and AIS regarding the maritime traffic within the port limits, and port weather stations regarding the environmental conditions. The operation is also remotely monitored by a shore-based operator in-the-loop based on operational data, such as the positions and speeds of the vessels involved, received from the autonomous tugboats and the AMS. The autonomous tugboats manoeuvre the vessel close to the designated berth in a predefined position and then the AMS is triggered by receiving the data from the autonomous tugboats that the vessel is in the berthing position. The AMS then secures the vessel at the berth and notifies the autonomous tugboats to disengage and also notifies the port that the berthing process has been successfully concluded.

4 Key Performance Indicators

An important part of the introduction of automation of any kind in the transport and logistics field is undoubtedly the evaluation of its potential impact. For this reason, this section presents and discusses the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) identified in AutoMoTIF for the use case of automated berthing and unberthing of freight vessels. The outlined KPIs cover several impact areas, i.e., operational efficiency, safety, environment, economy, and society (Hadjidimitriou, 2025).

The KPI framework for the use case is designed to assess various aspects of the automated system, ensuring a holistic evaluation that covers technical performance, environmental sustainability, economic viability, and societal impact. By leveraging both time-sensitive and resource-specific data, the framework aims to provide actionable insights into the performance of berthing and unberthing processes under varying conditions (Hadjidimitriou, 2025).

KPIs in **Operational Efficiency** measure the speed and smoothness of vessel maneuvering and docking. The following list of seven KPIs is critical for understanding how effectively the automated system reduces turnaround times and minimizes disruptions.

Manoeuvring and Docking Duration: This KPI measures the time required for a vessel to berth and unberth within the port area. Specifically, it captures the duration of the entire berthing process (i.e., from the anchorage point to being moored at the quay) and the unberthing process (i.e., from the quay to the sailing point). It provides a clear indication of the system's efficiency in reducing turnaround time and streamlining the port call process. Data collection will focus on the duration of operations across different weather conditions, ensuring a comprehensive performance assessment.

Number of Tugboat Movements: By tracking the number of directional changes or movements performed by tugboats during the berthing and unberthing processes, this indicator quantifies the operational dynamics. Monitoring these movements under varying weather conditions helps to pinpoint inefficiencies and potential areas for process improvement.

Safety-related metrics focus on the risk exposure for humans involved in berthing and unberthing processes. A key objective is to evaluate whether automation can lower the number of personnel required, thereby potentially reducing humans at risk.

Number of Humans at Risk: This safety metric assesses the number of crew members required on tugboats during port calls. The goal is to reduce human involvement in potentially hazardous operations through automation, thereby enhancing overall safety. The KPI is measured by counting the total number of personnel on board tugboats during these operations.

Environmental KPIs monitor the ecological footprint of the operation, including pollutant emissions and energy consumption. These measures help in assessing the sustainability of the automated process under different weather conditions.

Emissions: This environmental KPI quantifies the emissions produced by both the tugboats and the vessel during berthing and unberthing. Tracking the type and volume of emissions under different weather conditions allows for an assessment of the operation's environmental impact and helps identify areas for improvement.

Consumed Energy: Measuring the energy consumption of the tugboats during these operations provides another key environmental metric. The KPI focuses on total fuel consumption, highlighting the energy efficiency of the system and identifying opportunities to optimize fuel usage under various operational conditions.

Economic performance is evaluated by examining operational expenses. This KPI provides insight into the cost efficiency of running the tugboat services during berthing and unberthing, an important factor in overall project feasibility.

Operational Expenses of Tugboat Service: This metric tracks the cost associated with operating tugboats during berthing and unberthing. It is essential for evaluating the economic feasibility of the automated system. By monitoring these expenses, stakeholders can perform a detailed cost-benefit analysis to determine the financial viability of the process.

The **societal** impact is captured by assessing personnel requirements. This metric is crucial for understanding the potential workforce implications of transitioning from conventional to automated operations.

Personnel: This KPI measures the number of crew members needed to operate the tugboats. It serves as a direct indicator of the potential workforce reduction and improved operational safety

that automation might offer. The focus is on determining the optimal crewing levels required for efficient operation under the new automated system.

5 The AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture Framework for Digital Twins adapted to berthing and unberthing of freight vessels

One of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field of transport and logistics is the Digital Twin (DT), the rapid evolution of which has brought significant advancements, but it has also introduced new challenges that must be addressed in today's era that is characterized by an increased demand for open, modular, interoperable and scalable systems. As DTs transition to open architecture items as well, the complexity of managing diverse data sources, integrating legacy systems, and enabling advanced functionalities has grown significantly (Klar et al., 2024). Some additional challenges are ensuring security in data exchange and data governance and the required customization according to domain-specific requirements. The Open Digital Twin Reference Architecture framework that is developed in the context of the AutoMoTIF project aims to address these challenges.

The framework provides a structured and modular approach to designing DTs that meet the demands of interoperability and scalability while also offering a foundation for future advancements. By focusing on three key layers, namely, external integration, core functionality, and intermediary integration mechanisms, this architecture ensures a seamless flow of data and operations between external systems and the DTs' internal components (McKee, 2023). The Open Reference Architecture is specifically designed to overcome the limitations of traditional closed systems, which are often difficult to expand, providing a framework that is modular, interoperable, and expandable, enabling the seamless integration of external components, tools, and technologies from various providers. This openness does not imply that the system is "free" or unregulated; instead, it refers to the system's ability to interoperate with diverse external modules while maintaining a standardized core (Klar et al., 2024).

Figure 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the automated berthing and unberthing process for freight vessels at a port, adapted to the proposed framework. The process is structured across three interconnected layers: the outer, middle, and inner layers. These layers work together to create a detailed simulation of the use case, integrating real data and artificial intelligence models to optimize port operations.

The outer layer serves as the foundation, incorporating critical input parameters that influence the system's operations. These inputs include navigational data, continuous monitoring of unmanned tugboats and containerships, and the automation of mooring, berthing, and unberthing. Additionally, this layer accounts for various environmental and operational factors, such as weather conditions, vessel characteristics, tugboat specifications, predefined operating rules, and port infrastructure details. Lastly, it highlights the selected simulation platform for the deployment of the simulation of the use case, which is Unity 3D. These elements together establish the constraints and variables necessary to form the fundamental structure of our simulation.

The middle layer functions as the central processing unit of the system, managing data flows, system interactions, and communication between different components. The API Gateway ensures seamless and secure data exchange between external sources and the simulation environment, such as port data and port call information. Meanwhile, the data processing and transformation unit cleans, organizes, and structures raw input data, making it suitable for analysis and simulation. The workflow orchestrator synchronizes various tasks, ensuring the smooth execution of berthing and unberthing procedures, while the event handling and notification system enables users to select which scenario they want to execute. This includes options related to environmental conditions, port vessel traffic, and vessel size. Acting as a

bridge between the inner and outer layers, this layer ensures that all elements function in harmony to facilitate automation procedures.

The inner layer serves as the core of the simulation, integrating and coordinating all the preceding layers to execute the simulation process effectively. The Business Rules Engine ensures that all automated decisions comply with predefined operational regulations governing the berthing and unberthing of vessels. Furthermore, the Information Model structures the data flow, enabling smooth data retrieval and analysis related to the port, vessels, and tugboats. Simultaneously, the Simulation and Analysis Controller manages the execution of various user-selected scenarios, ensuring accurate and efficient simulation outcomes.

Figure 3: AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture diagram for the use case of automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

The benefits of developing the simulation for the AutoMoTIF automated port call process based on the reference architecture framework relates to the simulation itself, as well as to how the simulation can be used in future research. A standardized way to structure the simulation will support how it can be validated, while the modular architecture will provide the ability to test different models (e.g. for tugboat navigation) and efficiently integrate models through the Simulation & Analysis Controller and the Workflow orchestrator. Using the framework will also allow the simulation to be “DT-ready” and act as part of the digital twin of the automated port call process that can be used for supporting decisions in real-time.

Conclusion

This paper, which is part of the on-going research conducted in the context of the EU-funded AutoMoTIF project, contributes to the IPIC 2025 conference by exploring how automation and digitalization can enhance the efficiency, resilience, and sustainability of maritime freight transport, aligning with the broader goal of transforming supply chains through hyperconnectivity. It presents a use case which focuses on the automation of vessel port calls, a critical link between sea and land logistics. The research presented herein directly supports the large-scale implementation of Physical Internet by optimizing multimodal logistics operations, integrating emerging technologies and ensuring seamless data exchange across stakeholders. Moreover, the proposed open reference architecture for Digital Twins enables scalable, interoperable, and future-proof solutions that can contribute to the next generation of smart, hyperconnected maritime logistics ecosystems.

References

- Andrei N., Scarlat C. (2024): Marine applications: The Future of Autonomous Maritime Transportation and Logistics, IntechOpen eBooks, Feb. 2024.
- Aslam S., Michaelides M.P., Herodotou H. (2023): Berth allocation Considering Multiple Quays: A Practical approach using Cuckoo search Optimization, Journal of Marine Science and Engineering, v11(7), 1280. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11071280>
- De Alwis N., Nam H.-S. (2024): A way towards port automation: challenges and implications, WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs, Nov. 2024.
- Dekhne A., Hastings G., Murnane J., Neuhaus F. (2019): Automation in logistics: Big opportunity, bigger uncertainty, McKinsey & Company, Apr. 24, 2019.
- Fahim, P.B.M., Martinez de Ubago Alvarez de Sotomayor, M. Rezaei, J., Van Binsbergen, A., Nijdam, M., Tavasszy, L. (2021a): On the Evolution of Maritime Ports towards the Physical Internet, Futures, v13, 102834, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2021.102834>
- Fahim, P.B. M., Rezaei, J., Montreuil, B., Tavasszy, L. (2021): Port Performance Evaluation and Selection in the Physical Internet, Transport Policy, v124, 83-94, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2021.07.013>
- Hadjidimitriou, S. (2025): AutoMoTIF D3.1 Evaluation Framework
- IEC Telecom (2023): Hybrid solutions for seamless connectivity at sea: The GEO/LEO paradigm. Retrieved from <https://iec-telecom.com/en/news/hybrid-solutions-for-seamless-connectivity-at-sea-the-geo-leo-paradigm/>
- Klar R., Arvidsson N., Angelakis V. (2024): Digital Twins' Maturity: The Need for Interoperability, IEEE Systems Journal, v18(1), 713-724.
- Lind M., Ward R., Bergmann M., Bjørn-Andersen N., Watson R.T., Haraldson S., Andersen T., Michaelides M. (2019): PortCDM: Validation of the concept and next steps, Unpublished.
- Marine-Pilots (2023): Road Towards Autonomous Ship Handling with Tugs. Retrieved from <https://www.marine-pilots.com/articles/13470-road-towards-autonomous-ship-handling-with-tugs>
- McKee D. (2023): Platform Stack Architectural Framework: An Introductory Guide, Digital Twin Consortium White Paper.
- Montreuil B. (2011): Towards a Physical Internet: Meeting the Global Logistics Sustainability Grand Challenge, Logistics Research, v3, no2-3, 71-87, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12159-011-0045-x>

- Port Technology (2023): Port of Rotterdam implements Smart Mooring Solution. Retrieved from <https://www.porttechnology.org/news/port-of-rotterdam-implements-smart-mooring-solution/>
- Prasad S., Saragiotis P., Ollivier P. (2023): Port Community Systems. Lessons from Global Experience, World Bank Group.
- Segura, L., Arona, M. and Anglès, M. (2025): AutoMoTIF D1.1 AutoMoTIF playground and vision.
- Shi X., Tao D., Voß S. (2011): RFID technology and its application to port-based container logistics, *Journal of Organizational Computing*, v21(4), 332–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10919392.2011.614202>
- Yang M., Fu M., Zhang Z. (2021): The adoption of digital technologies in supply chains: Drivers, process and impact, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, v169, 120795

Disclaimer

The AutoMoTIF project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Program, through the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the powers delegated from the European Commission and under Grant Agreement No 101147693.

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers, and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services. While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors or any other participant in the AutoMoTIF consortium make no warranty of any kind regarding this material including but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no responsibility or liability with respect to this document, which is merely representing the authors’ view.